

Particle-Wave Duality and Two Types of Measurements

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We argue that in classical mechanics there exist at least two types of measurements of a constant moving particle. (This may be extended to an accelerating one.) First there is the $x(t)$ description which is sometimes considered a complete description of the mechanical case. This implies one may measure position and time of the particle successively and thus know about its behaviour in space and time. We argue that there is a second measurement which is not one of space or time, but rather of impulse. A constant moving particle may strike a foil at any place in its path at any time (if one has an ensemble of such classical particles) and the foil will “recognize” that it has been hit by a momentum p .

In quantum mechanics we argue that there are also two types of measurement for a free particle. The first is the identical momentum impulse measurement i.e. the particle strikes a foil which recognizes it has momentum p . There seems to be no quantum feature to this. Such a measurement has already been performed classically for photons. This is the “particle” like measurement which has nothing to do with wave features. A. Einstein in 1905 in his work on the photoelectric effect already noted that particle type behaviour of a photon. The second type of measurement deals with spatial features which are very different from $x(t)$. A quantum free particle is represented by $\exp(ipx)$ which contains “ p ” which may be measured by an impulse. We argue, however, that spatial features, unlike those for a classical wave in which the medium and wave disturbance are separated, require interference i.e. the summing of $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(ip_1 x)$ or $\exp(ip_2 x)$ or $\exp(ip(x+b))$ or $\exp(ip_1(x+b_1))$. Thus $\exp(ipx)$ behaves like a complex probability. Mathematically it has a modulus of 1 which is said to be linked to equal probability for it to be at any x . Why should this be relevant? We argue that it is because of the impulse measurement which indicates that a p hit may occur at any x . We further argue that $\exp(ipx)$ behaves as part of a projection operator because it is orthogonal to other $\exp(ip_1 x)$'s. It is this orthogonality which seems to allow for one to build a probability medium, but requires $W^*(x)W(x)=P(x)$. In such a case, $a^*(p)a(p)$ terms create the medium from which probability may be added and removed by cross terms $\exp(ip_1 x) \exp(ip_2 x)$. Orthogonality ensures that overall what is added and removed cancel. Thus there are two levels of probability, one at $W(x)$ linked to OR situations created by interactions which reveal the spatial nature of a quantum free particle and the other $W^*(x)W(x)$.

Light

Originally Newton considered light to act as a classical particle. At his time classical waves were known to exist such as water waves etc. Later diffraction and interference patterns of light showed it behaved as a wave, namely that it reproduced the same patterns that classical waves such as water waves do. In 1905 Einstein suggested that even though interference experiments demonstrate wave properties of light, the energy of light could not be spread out over the wave region. In other words there was a second kind of measurement, namely an impulse p one, which could occur at any point. Thus a particle-wave duality exists and different kinds of experiments may reveal features of each.

Classical Waves

Classical waves such as waves on a string, water waves and sound have nonlocal features because part of the medium, which does not move with the wave, behaves in one region in a certain way (e.g. a trough) and in another in the opposite way (e.g. crest). The wave carries energy and momentum and is linked to the impulse measurement, but the independent medium is linked to nonlocal spatial measurements (akin to $x(t)$ for a classical mechanical particle).

Quantum Free Particle

A single quantum free particle carries a momentum of p and therefore should be measurable via an impulse experiment which is not linked to spatial features (local or nonlocal).

As a result, one only needs to know p for such a measurement, but this gives no information about spatial behaviour. How is information about space-time obtained?

In (1) we argued that if v is written as x/t and x and t varied independently in either the relativistic or nonrelativistic free particle action $S = -m_0 t \sqrt{1-v^2}$ ($c=1$) or $S = t \cdot 5mv$, then:

$$dA/dx \text{ partial} = p \text{ and } dA/dt \text{ partial} = -E \text{ so } A = -Et + px \text{ ((1))}$$

In other words x and t are treated as independent. Converting ((1)) into eigenvalue equations yields:

$$-i d/dx \text{ partial} \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA) \text{ and } i d/dt \text{ partial} \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA) \text{ ((2))}$$

The spatial part $\exp(ipx)$ is linked to a space measurement. The presence of a specific p implies there is an impulse measurement which is not linked to space. Unlike a classical wave, these two cannot be decoupled. There is no stationary medium, the particle itself is the medium. Thus one has two types of measurements, but a possible contradiction. The p impulse measurement can occur at any x and there cannot be any spatial variation. $\exp(ipx)$, however, suggests spatial variation, but the "catch" seems to be that it is two dimensional and has:

$$\text{Modulus } (\exp(ipx)) = 1 \text{ ((3))}$$

One might argue that this is simply a mathematical property, but traditionally it is said to represent the fact that the particle has the same probability to be present at any point x . We argue it means the particle has the same probability to impart an impulse linked to p at any point x , while still having spatial dependence.

A question now arises: How does one measure this x variation?

Unlike classical mechanics, measurements of $x(t)$ are not possible because interactions such as those with the walls of single slit, double slit, potential impulse from $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ or a Bohm-Aharonov interaction which leaves p unchanged change the free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ must be compared with another unchanged wavefunction in order for a

measurement to occur. In other words interference must occur. (Note there are soft measurements which do not have this requirement, but here we consider the usual hard measurements.) Thus:

Type 1 Measurement: Impulse measurements of p may occur at any x point. Thus if a spatial function linked to a Type 2 measurement exists, it must point to this. For a classical wave, there is a decoupled spatial variation and momentum and energy flow in the wave. Thus a sound wave etc may impart an impulse of p at any point and at the same time the medium has nonlocal spatial dependence. This is not the case for the quantum free particle. It must represent both types of measurements. We argue that this is the reason for the $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$.

Type 2 Measurement: To measure the spatial behaviour of a quantum free particle one requires interference i.e. an OR probability situation:

$$A_1 \exp(ip_1 x) + A_2 \exp(ip_2 x) \text{ or } A_1 \exp(ip_1 x) + B \exp(ip_2(x+b)) \text{ etc } ((4))$$

It is this combination which indicates that some kind of interaction has occurred which leads to nonlocal shifting of probability. In this case:

$$P(x) = (A_1 \exp(ip_1 x) + A_2 \exp(ip_2 x))^* (A_1 \exp(ip_1 x) + A_2 \exp(ip_2 x)) \quad ((5))$$

where $*$ is the complex conjugate. One now finds different spatial densities at different x points, but a type 2 measurement is still linked to a type 1 measurement. The change in physical spatial density means that on average there will be fewer impulse hits at certain x points than at others. In other words:

Function(x) $P(x)$ gives the overall average where Function(x) could be $KE_{ave}(x) = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W = \{ \text{Sum over } p \frac{a(p) p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx) \} / \{ \text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx) \}$. Where $W(x) =$ wavefunction. ((6))

Orthonormality and the Wavefunction as a Projection

Consider the function $\exp(ipx)$. It is orthogonal to other $\exp(ip_1 x)$'s and we argue that this is a key feature of quantum mechanics namely that not only does $\exp(ipx)$ form an orthogonal basis, but $W_n(x)$ where $W_n(x)$ is a solution of the time-dependent Schrodinger equation also does. Different $V(x)$ potentials yield different families of $W_n(x)$.

Consider a function $f(x)$. Then from a Fourier analysis:

$$f(x) = \text{Sum over } p b(p) \exp(ipx)$$

Next consider shifting this function in space i.e. $f(x) \rightarrow f(x+a)$. This may be written two ways at least:

$f(x+a) = \int dx \left\{ \sum_p c_1 c_1 \exp(ip x') \exp(-ipx) \right\} f(x)$ where x' is finally set to $x+a$.

$C_1 c_1$ is a normalization factor. In other words the term in $\{ \}$ behaves as a Dirac functional or distribution $\delta(x'-x)$. By integrating over x , the orthonormal feature eliminates $\exp(ipx)$ obtaining its coefficient which may then be linked with $\exp(ip(x+a))$.

The second way is: $f(x+a) = f(x) \exp(a d/dx) f(x)$.

Thus $\exp(ipx)$ and d/dx are linked in this manner as well.

In the above section it was noted one may form a linear combination:

$$W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((6))$$

If $\exp(ipx)$ is thought of as a kind of probability, then ((6)) represents an OR situation. The orthogonality of $\exp(ipx)$ is key, however, because one may multiply $W(x)$ by $\exp(-ipx)$ and integrate to obtain $a(p)$. Locally $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ip_1 x)$ is not 1 like $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$, but it integrates to 0. This means there must be positive and negative regions over x . In other words probability is increased in some areas and decreased in others as shown in single slit and two slit experiments and bound states such as the oscillator. Unlike a classical wave where some material is pulled out from one place and added to another, for a sum ((6)) each $\exp(ipx)$ produces some pure probability from which some probability may be added or subtracted. Thus locally one has probability humps and troughs, but $W^*(x)W(x)$ is real and positive for all x . After the final integration, all cross terms $\exp(ip_1 x) \exp(ip_2 x)$ drop out and one is left with $\sum_p a^*(p)a(p)$ which may be set to 1. Locally, however, the case is very different.

Thus we argue that it is the orthonormality of the $\exp(ipx)$ which leads to $W^*(x)W(x)$ representing physical spatial density. If one only considers ((6)) which is like considering a classical wave (because for bound systems the complex part adds to 0) there are positive humps and negative for each $\sin(px)$. A negative hump is created by removing medium which does not move with the wave and a crest is created by adding the same material to a different region.

For a quantum bound situation, one may have $\cos(px)$ form $\pm p$ and it too has humps and crests which cancel if one integrates over x , but this is not density. There is no medium which is removed and added. It is only through $W^*(x)W(x)$ that one creates probability pieces $a^*(p)a(p) \exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$ from which one may remove and add probability through $\exp(ip_1 x)\exp(ip_2 x)$. Overall due to orthogonality, what is added and what is removed cancel (over all x). Thus we argue that orthogonality (orthonormality) is responsible for the form $W^*(x)W(x)=P(x)$. $W(x)$ the wavefunction is sometimes called the square root of probability, but it is both a kind of probability of its own and part of a projection operator. The projection operator, however, requires both $W^*(x)$ and $W(x)$.

Analogy of $W(x) = \sum_n b_n(E_n) \exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x)$ and $W(x)$

If one considers $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ one may ask how one may change from one p to another. $V(x)$, a potential, allows for this i.e. there is an interaction which creates many $\exp(ipx)$ s which interfere as time and x are treated as independent. $W^*(x)W(x)$ has local density, but is really a projection type of object because if one integrates all cross terms $\exp(ip_1 x) \exp(ip_2 x)$ drop out and one only has $a^*(p)a(p)$ type terms.

If one considers $W(x) = \sum_n b_n(E_n) \exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x)$ a similar situation occurs. In this case $W_n(x)$ replaces $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$, but both are orthonormal sets. Furthermore there is again an interaction namely with a photon (phonon etc) bath which allows the system to jump from $W_{n1}(x)$ to $W_{n2}(x)$ etc. One again has a projection operator type of situation and so $W^*(x)W(x)$ integrated over x removes cross terms and only leaves $b^*_{n}(E_n)b_n(E_n)$ type terms. Thus $P(x)$ is again equal to $W^*(x)W(x)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that the particle wave duality idea seems to already exist in classical physics and is based on two kinds of measurements. The first is an impulse measurement which responds only to p momentum. It is not concerned with spatial motion. The second measurement type for a free classical mechanical particle is $x(t)$ which determines spatial behaviour. Already in classical physics one has waves. The waves carry momentum and are linked to the impulse type of measurement. The medium does not move with the wave and is linked to a spatial type of measurement of crests and troughs.

A quantum free particle also is associated with these two types of measurements. Its wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ contains p which is linked to an impulse measurement which has nothing to do with spatial behaviour. There is no medium however, so $\exp(ipx)$ which displays spatial information should also suggest that the impulse is the same at all x . We argue that $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)=1$ represents the same p impulse at all x .

We also argue that $\exp(ipx)$ is a kind of probability which describes spatial behaviour, but one may only measure this if there is some kind of interaction leading to interference of the particle with itself or another particle. Single slit diffraction, two slit interference and bound state interference are examples as is the Bohm Aharonov case. This leads to the question: Why is $W^*(x)W(x)$ needed to obtain $P(x)$? For a classical wave $\cos(px)$ is good enough, but this describes the medium which is not moving with the wave. For a quantum free particle there is no medium. The medium is probability so one needs to remove some and add it elsewhere like a medium. $\exp(ipx)$ contains $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$, but these are both negative and positive and do not solve the problem.

We argue that it is the orthonormality of $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$ that leads to a solution. $\exp(ipx)$ behaves like a kind of probability so one may add in OR situations. $\exp(ipx)$, however, is part of a projection operator because it is orthonormal to other $\exp(ip_1 x)$ s. Thus $W^*(x)W(x)$ gives a set of $a^*(p)a(p)$ values which act like a probability medium. Cross terms $\exp(ip_1 x)\exp(ip_2 x)$ may add and remove some of this probability, but due to orthonormality the amount removed cancels the amount added when one integrates over all space.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Lagrangian/Action Formalism as a Flow Scheme? (preprint, zenodo, 2021)